

TA'LIM OLUVCHILARNING MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI FANIGA BO'LGAN QIZIQISHLARINI KOMPETENSIYALIY YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA OSHIRISH MUAMMOLARI.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada talabalarning fanga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini kompetensiyaliy yondashuvlar asosida oshirish. Elektron ta'lim resurslarini yaratish va ularning yordamida ta'lim oluvchilarning egallagan bilimlarini mustaxkamlash muammolari o'rganildi. Ta'lim oluvchilarning ma'lumotlar bazasi faniga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini oshirish, bilimlarni sinash va mustaxkamlash muammolarini aralash turdagi topshiriqlar tayyorlash orqali bartaraf etish yo'llari ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim vositalari, kompetensiyaliy yondashuv, aralash topshiriqlar, elektron ta'lim vositalari, iSpring, MyTest.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИНТЕРЕСА СТУДЕНТОВ К БАЗЕ ДАННЫХ НА ОСНОВЕ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТНЫХ ПОДХОДОВ.

Аннотация. Данная статья направлена на повышение интереса учащихся к науке посредством компетентностных подходов. Изучены проблемы создания электронных образовательных ресурсов и их использования для закрепления знаний обучающихся. Существуют способы повысить интерес учащихся к науке о базах данных, а также решить проблему проверки и закрепления знаний за счет подготовки смешанных типов заданий.

Ключевые слова: учебные пособия, компетентностный подход, смешанные задания, электронные средства обучения, iSpring, MyTest.

PROBLEMS OF INCREASING STUDENTS' INTEREST TO THE DATABASE ON THE BASIS OF COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACHES.

Abstract. This article is aimed at increasing students' interest in science through competence-based approaches. The problems of creating electronic educational resources and their use to consolidate the knowledge of students are studied. There are ways to increase students' interest in database science, as well as solve the problem of testing and consolidating knowledge by preparing mixed types of tasks.

Key words: teaching aids, competency-based approach, mixed tasks, e-learning tools, iSpring, MyTest.

INTRODUCTION

Today, with the increasing capabilities of computer and information and communication technologies, there are opportunities to create educational tools and use them to improve the quality of education, increase the interest of students. The main goal is to achieve high efficiency in the learning of students. It is known that a person remembers 10% of the information when reading the source, 20% when hearing, and 50% when watching the process. The capabilities of modern computer technology allow learners to virtually analyze the learning object.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The necessary didactic tools for the organization of education in the educational process are selected taking into account such factors as the purpose, content, type of education, type of education. It is important to identify the factors that need to be considered in this process and use the right tools. Methods of observation, comparison, experiment, and generalization were used throughout the study.

RESULTS

Implementing a competency-based approach to increase students' interest in database science will help shape their future professional competencies. Let us first analyze the concept of a competent approach. The traditional approach is that in the learning process, the teacher introduces the basic concepts of the topic being studied, including the main content and theoretical knowledge of the subject being studied. The content and basic concepts of education are directly accepted by the learners, based on the topic covered in the syllabus. Academic and professional knowledge is studied and mastered in accordance with established scientific laws. Practical training and laboratory work are aimed at acquiring the planned knowledge and achieving the desired results. Independent work is organized on the basis of topics identified by students, and the selected topics are set in terms of the content of the subject. A competency-based approach is one in which the teacher identifies general (strategic) tasks with learners during the learning process, describing the expected outcomes needed for future activities. The student and the teacher work together and independently to develop a level of analysis of motivationally interesting topics and materials. Learners select important information to solve a given problem and look for solutions to a pre-prepared task or problem, such as the process of solving a life problem. Academic and professional knowledge is based on research in the field of problem solving. Practical and laboratory work allows you to compare the results and independently choose the solution. Independent work is based on the study of life problems, and the knowledge acquired through the main content of science is used to solve the problem.

Many interactive methods and tools have been developed and a lot of research has been done to increase students' interest in classroom and extracurricular activities. The process of testing and evaluating students' knowledge is important not only to monitor the learning process, but also to increase their interest in science. Therefore, in the preparation of control and knowledge testing tasks, it is necessary to pay attention to interactivity, game methods, puzzles and mixed training. Based on this, we create a set of mixed tasks by preparing mixed tasks in the field of database science. They are more effective than other types of tasks. [3]

E-learning tools are a set of all electronic tools used to organize the learning process. In the process of testing and consolidating knowledge, various district models of electronic control devices have been developed. Examples include quizzes, various game programs, interactive assignments, and more. Among the modern programs that create such electronic tools are Ispring, MyTest. In the Spring program you can prepare 11 different types of assignments of different shapes. The advantage of mixed tasks over one type of task is that a large number of tasks of the same type can lead to boredom or fatigue. Mixed-type assignments develop the ability to be ready for different tasks, to think creatively, and to be ready for different situations.

Advantages of mixed tasks prepared in iSpring program

1. Optionally use different tasks in one set of tasks.

2. Ability to prepare assignments on the basis of various text, video, audio and graphic data.
3. Ability to place mathematical formulas and problems.
4. Develop students' ability to think logically by completing a variety of tasks.
5. Develop students' creative approach to assignments.
6. Ease of application interface.
7. Popularity and accessibility for each user. [4]

And we can cite others. In the first part of my assignment, the question is answered by choosing one of the yes or no answers. In this way, the student demonstrates his or her unique approach to the question. In our second assignment, the student completes three different test assignments. We used a test with a moderate level of difficulty. In the third stage, the student works on several options, the answer of which may be one or more of them, or all of them will cause the student to think. In the next step, the student completes the task by combining the interrelationships of different considerations.

Completing such a variety of tasks will not only increase students' interest in science, but also help them develop their intellectual abilities. Confronted with a variety of tasks, they are able to assess the situation and find the right way out of difficult situations. This ability is one of the most important requirements for any database professional. [1]

DISCUSSION

The impact of a traditional type of e-assignment on the psychological process of students and their effectiveness in the process of consolidating knowledge were studied. In addition, there was an increase in students' psychological emotions and interest in science in the performance of mixed tasks. It has been observed that the widespread application of this type of task in all disciplines is more effective than the use of other types of tasks, as it has shown its high efficiency. The literature on the subject was analyzed and the opinions of scholars on the subject were studied. Legislation in the field was analyzed. Based on this, we recommend the following:

- The process of testing and consolidating students' knowledge is different from the control of knowledge, because the student must first evaluate himself objectively. Therefore, it is advisable to use more visual and virtual assignments in the process of testing and consolidating knowledge;

- Each task should first of all require a certain level of logical thinking and reasoning. First of all, it promotes the development of students' logical thinking;

- It is important to pay attention to the diversity and structure of the questions. Each time a completely different type of question arises, the student becomes more interested and ready for different situations.

It is up to the user to decide which of the modern applications to use, but the desired goal can be achieved. Research on this case is ongoing.

Based on the analysis analyzed above, the use of a differentiated and non-standard set of tasks in the assessment of competence is highly effective. Here are some examples from a set of tasks to assess knowledge on the topic of creating a database:

Test questions	
What is the data relation model?	A) Representation of data in tabular form. B) Network representation of data. C) Sort the data.
What is the answer given by the database management system?	A) MS Access, MySQL B) PhotoShop, Paint C) Google Chrome
Logical questions	
If the data is collected, sorted, systematized, and tabulated, what model of database should be used?	
Problematic question	
Continuous data entry into a database stores a large amount of information. This creates a memory and speed problem. How to organize your data management can help prevent these problems.	

The use of tasks of various mixed forms not only strengthens the testing of knowledge, but also serves to form professional competence by working with problem situations and problem questions, finding solutions to them.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the process of coverage of each subject and topic, first of all, the student's high level of knowledge and the formation of high professional competence will help them to become high-potential and competitive professionals in the future. First of all, it is a key factor in the development of society. After all, the training of highly qualified pedagogical staff, first of all, ensures the development of potential young people in the future.

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